

Enhancing Transdiagnostic Protective Factors in the Management of Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder through Acceptance and Commitment Therapy

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Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD) is a severe and distressing mental health condition characterized by presence of repetitive obsessional thoughts and compulsions. Despite the well-confirmed efficacy of the existing traditional therapeutic interventions, there remains a critical need to explore third-wave therapies that target positive psychological aspects alongside Obsessive compulsive symptoms. The current study investigated the efficacy of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) in improving psychological flexibility, self-compassion, equanimity, and valued living among individuals diagnosed with OCD. The study sample was taken across tertiary care and private mental health centres in Jaipur, Rajasthan. A sample of 14 participants was allocated to an intensive ACT program consisting of 12-20 sessions over a 6-10-week period. Standardized psychometric tools were administered to assess clinical outcomes, including the Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS) (Goodman et al., 1989), Neff's Self-Compassion Scale (Neff, 2003), the Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (AAQ-II), the Equanimity Questionnaire (Bond et al., 2011), and the Valued Living Questionnaire (VLQ) (Wilson & Groom, 2002). Paired-samples t-tests revealed statistically significant improvements across all the variables. Significant reductions were observed in OCD severity ($M = 3.36, SD = 2.70, p < .001$). Furthermore, participants showed significant improvement in self-compassion ($p < .001$), equanimity ($p < .001$), and psychological flexibility ($p = .001$). Improvements in valued living were also significant, including value importance ($p < .001$), consistency ($p < .001$), and total values scores ($p = .001$). These findings suggest ACT to be a highly effective intervention for not only alleviating obsessional symptoms but also for positive mental health growth.

Keywords: OCD, acceptance and commitment therapy, psychological flexibility, self-compassion, equanimity

Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is a mental disorder consisting of obsessions and compulsions. Obsessions are repetitive, intrusive, irrational, and distressing ideas, thoughts, or urges and impulses. Compulsions are recurrent behaviours or mental acts that individuals feel compelled to carry out to avoid or lessen suffering or to forestall some feared event or condition. Uncontrollable thoughts, images, or impulses that are persistent and recurrent are the clinical characteristics of an obsession. While wanting to escape these thoughts, the person is unable to do so. The thoughts are unpleasant, intrusive, and illogical in character. These thoughts are accompanied by uncomfortable emotions like fear, uncertainty, guilt, shame, etc. Compulsion is characterised by repetitive mental and physical acts and the recurrence of certain behaviour or beliefs that a person owns to neutralize, combat, or relieve themselves from the anxiety elicited

by the obsessions. In the absence of a more effective coping mechanism, people with OCD tend to rely on the compulsion as a means of brief relief from their obsessions, even though they understand the relief the compulsion brings in temporary (Stein et al., 2016).

According to Hayes et al. (1999), values are "freely chosen, verbally constructed consequences of ongoing, dynamic, evolving patterns of activity, which establish dominant reinforcers for that activity that are intrinsic in engagement in the valued behavioural pattern itself. Value describes the degree of significance of something or an activity in order to choose the best course of action, the best way to live, or to explain the motivation behind various behaviours (Schwartz, 1992). Human behaviour is guided by values. Values serve as the foundation for identifying the level of awareness that influences and motivates (Schwartz, 1992). Michelson et al. (2011) found that restrictions in valued action contributed unique variance to diminished quality of life over and above the contributions of gender, symptom severity, experiential avoidance, distress about emotions, and depression comorbidity in patients.

Wetterneck et al. (2013) revealed significant relationships between OCD severity and self-compassion, courage and valued living. Rather than dismissing our suffering or berating ourselves with self-criticism, self-compassion means being kind and sympathetic towards ourselves when we fail, suffer, or feel inadequate (Neff, 2003). Compassion literally translates as "suffering with." When someone claims to have compassion for another person, it is assumed that person either voluntarily or involuntarily "suffers" with that other (Gilbert, 2009). Self-

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compassion acts as a safeguard for those who have a sensitive heart and are empathetic, preventing them from sinking into a debilitating sense of worthlessness due to their failure to help the person who is suffering or in great need (Neff, 2003). Eichholz et al. (2020) concluded that there was a negative relationship between self-compassion and emotion regulation difficulties. Emotional regulation predicted symptom severity when controlling for obsessive beliefs and depression. Van et al. (2010) stated that the self-compassion is a robust predictor of symptom severity and quality of life. Study further revealed that self-compassion predicts more variance in psychopathology than mindfulness. It also showed that self-compassion reflects complex nature of relationship between mindful constructs and health.

According to Kashdan and Rotterburg (2010), psychological flexibility is "the measurement of how a person adapts to fluctuating situational demands, re-configures mental resources, shifts perspective, and balances competing desires needs, and life domains." Psychological flexibility, according to Hayes et al. (2004), is "contacting the present moment as a conscious human being, and, based on what that situation affords, acting in accordance with one's chosen values" Bond et al. (2006). Psychological flexibility is described as "the process of contacting the present moment as a conscious human being and persisting in or changing behaviour in the service of chosen values" (Hayes et al., 2006) in the ACT model. In layman's words, psychological flexibility is essentially awareness of the present moment and behavioural change that moves towards behaviours based on ideals. Thompson et al. (2021) revealed that greater self-as-content was associated with more severe mental contamination and unacceptable thoughts.

Equanimity referred to as "neutral feeling," a mental experience that is neither pleasant nor unpleasant and does neither intensify or detract from the present state of mind (Bodhi, 2000).

Scriptures, religious doctrines, and philosophical systems all regard equanimity as a mental condition and essential lesson (James, 1910). However, psychology has only just begun to pay attention to it. An even-minded mental state or dispositional propensity towards all experiences or objects, independent of their affective valence (pleasant, unpleasant, or neutral), or source, has been described as equanimity in one of the seminal publications (Desbordes et al., 2015).

Wongpakaran et al. (2021) suggested that the effect of perceived stress and neuroticism on depression can be mitigated by increasing levels of equanimity. Dambrun and Shankland (2020) also revealed positive correlations between the components of equanimity and both formal and informal mindfulness practices in stress reduction.

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) is a therapy technique that aims to increase psychological flexibility via the use of commitment and behaviour modification processes as well as acceptance and mindfulness processes (Hayes et al., 1999).

According to acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT), one can act without first eradicating or altering his sentiments (Hayes et al., 1999). This therapy is predicated on the idea that a person can witness oneself experiencing a sensation while still acting, as opposed to battling the emotion associated with a conduct. The most effective strategy, according to acceptance-based approaches, could be to accept while changing rather than choosing to change only. Contrary to methods that try to regulate or alter these cognitions, ACT therapists use techniques that help clients step back (or "defuse")

from the impact of negative thoughts and beliefs. Instead of concentrating on diminishing the reported clinical symptoms, the therapy's major goal is to assist the client in leading a "vital" and values-consistent life (Hayes et al., 1999).

Acceptance, diffusion, touch with the present moment, the self as context, committed action, and values were the six basic components identified by Hayes et al. (Hayes, 1999). These parts are related to one another and rely on one another rather than occurring in a sequential order. This results in a fluid paradigm that calls for therapist flexibility (Webster, 2011). ACT was found to be more effective in increasing psychological flexibility and this superiority was maintained in follow-up (Yazdi et al., 2014). Vakili and Gharraee (2014) have too found Acceptance and Commitment Therapy effective in treating obsessive compulsive disorder and symptoms of depression and anxiety. The current study focuses of evaluating how the intervention can promote symptom reduction and enhance positive mental state and value oriented behaviour.

The rationale of study stems from lack of Indian researches focusing on third wave therapies, particularly ACT in the management of Obsessive-Compulsive disorder, focusing not just to see the efficacy in symptom reduction but also in improvement in positive mental health states and quality of life through fostering self-compassion, equanimity, psychological flexibility and valued living.

Aims of the Study

- To assess the efficacy of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy in patients with obsessive compulsive disorder
- To examine the effect of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy on the positive psychological attributes in patients of the study.

Hypotheses of the Study

For the purpose of fulfilling the above aims, the following hypothesis had been formulated:

- *H1*: There is a difference in the pre- & post-scores of the Acceptance and Commitment Therapy interventions on
- *H1A*: OCD
- *H1B*: Values
- *H1C*: Self-Compassion
- *H1D*: Psychological Flexibility
- *H1E*: Equanimity

Method

Participants

The sample of the study comprised of 14 patients, both males and females, diagnosed with obsessive-compulsive disorder. The sample was selected using purposive sampling technique, as per the following criteria of inclusion and exclusion.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed according to ICD 10 diagnostic criteria (WHO, 1992)
- Patients with mild to moderate severity of OCD
- Age between 25-45 years
- Patients stabilized on medication for 2 months
- Minimum educational qualification of 12th standard
- Ability to comprehend English language

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of Organicity, Epilepsy, any other neurological disorders or Intellectual disability
- Patients with history of serious medical conditions
- Patients with Dysthymia or Depression with Psychotic Features
- Patients with history of any other serious psychological disorder
- Patients diagnosed concurrently with any Personality Disorder or Alcohol or Psychoactive Substance use disorder
- Patients having undergone any psychological intervention for OCD in last year
- Patients with severe OCD
- Patients undergone ECT treatment in past or present

Research Design

Study was carried out based on pre post design.

Measures

Case History Performa (developed for the study) This includes the detailed case history of the patient which comprises of their socio-demographic profile, chief symptoms and Complaints, History of current illness, negative history, personal history and family history, premorbid personality and temperament and mental status examination.

Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsion Scale (Goodman et al., 1989): It is a semi-structured interview which assesses symptom severity of OCD. It is measured on a 10-item symptom severity that measures symptom intensity independent of symptom subtype and a checklist of typical obsessions and compulsions. A score of 07 indicates subclinical symptoms, 8-15 means mild symptoms, 16-23 imply moderate symptoms, 24-31 severe symptoms, and 32-40 extreme symptoms. The total score is between 0 to 40. Additionally, there is a subscale score (range 0-20) for obsessions and compulsions which can be obtained separately from the scale. Goodman et al. (1989) validated this scale by observing a significant correlation between the Y-BOCS and two separate measures of OCD. OCD symptom changes can affect Y-BOCS. Additionally, the Y-BOCS exhibits good interrater reliability and great internal consistency (Goodman et al., 1989).

Valued Living Questionnaire (Wilson & Groom, 2002): This self-statement scale is a measure of valued life. Ten life areas are included in the scale, which is used to determine whether or not individuals live their life in accordance with the values. The subscales "Importance" and "Coherence" are the two that exist in the scale. Ten items make up each subscale, and each item was assessed on a 10-point Likert scale (1 being not important to 10 being extremely important). According to the scale's scoring system, high scores are suggestive of a life that is very value-oriented. The Importance and Consistency answers for each category are multiplied, and the average of those values is then computed to determine the Valued Living composite. The Valued Living Composite scores that are obtained can vary from 10 to 100. Test-retest reliability for this tool has been credible (Cotter, 2011).

The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire II (Bond et al., 2011) This tool is a 7-item measure of psychological inflexibility. The alternatives for responses are 1 for "Never true" and 7 for "Always true." For instance, "I'm afraid of my feelings" is an AAQ-II item. Elevated overall scores on the AAQ-II correlate with increased experience avoidance, psychological rigidity, and probable

psychological discomfort. Low scores indicate greater psychological adaptability. The adequate discriminant validity of the AAQ-II is demonstrated. Better psychometric consistency is seen in the AAQ-II ($r=.97$), which seems to measure the same notion as the AAQ-I (Bond et al., 2011).

Self Compassion Scale (Neff, 2003): This scale entails 26-items with 6 subscales. The scales are self-kindness subscale that has 5 items, the 5-item self-judgment subscale, common humanity subscale constitutes of 4 items along with the 4-item isolation subscale, mindfulness subscale and over-identification subscale. It is a 5-point scale from 1= "almost never" to 5= "almost always". The scoring method comprises of calculating the Mean scores on the six subscales to create an overall self-compassion score. The scale has shown to have a good internal and test retest reliability in research, (Neff, 2003). The internal consistency reliability obtained was a = .94.

Equanimity Questionnaire (Shires & Cayoun, 2021): This is a 16-item self-report measure. It was developed for adults 18 years of age and above. It is a useful tool in the therapeutic context to examine the factors of experiential avoidance and a client's emotional reactivity. There are two subscales in the tool: Experiential acceptance (items 18): this refers to a mindset that accepts all internal experiences (thoughts, feelings, bodily sensations, etc.) without trying to resist or cling to them. Non-Reactivity (items 916): This scale measures a person's lack of reaction to situations that hinder them from being attached to or averse to them (e.g., ideas, emotions). According to Rogers et al. (2021), the scale possesses strong internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = .88), test-retest reliability over a period of two to six weeks, and both convergent and divergent validity.

Therapy Module

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy

Week 1-2: Psychoeducation and Orientation: Introduced participants to OCD, its cognitive-behavioral underpinnings, and the principles of ACT. This was also the pre-intervention phase wherein the purpose was to also Conduct initial assessments to establish baselines for OCD severity, psychological flexibility, and experiential avoidance. This psychoeducation session also focused on the nature of thoughts, emotions, and behaviors in OCD.

Week 3-5: Core ACT Processes: Mindfulness Training: The session focused on teaching mindfulness practices to enhance present-moment awareness. Exercises included breath awareness, body scans exercises, and mindful observation of thoughts.

Cognitive Defusion: This session introduced techniques to help participants observe thoughts without attachment and judgment. Exercises included labelling of thoughts, the metaphors (e.g., "Leaves on a Stream"), and vocalizing thoughts in different tones were the techniques used for it.

Acceptance: This session focused on encouraging openness to internal experiences without avoidance. Exercises involved practicing willingness to experience uncomfortable intrusive thoughts and feelings as they arise in the individual.

Week 6-8: Values and Committed Action

Values Clarification: The focus in these sessions was to assist participants in identifying personal values and explaining the rationale of how it's important to align one's daily actions according to them. We Used exercises like the "Values Card Sort" to prioritize life domains.

Committed Action: After assessing the values of each patient, action plans were developed to engage in meaningful activities despite OCD-related discomfort. The goal setting was done through the SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) approach, where it was considered that the person's goals aligned with values.

Week 9-11: Integration and Application: These sessions combined mindfulness, acceptance, and values-based strategies to address OCD symptoms directly. Experiential exercises were taught to practice skills in real-life contexts. This phase also introduced exposure-based exercises within the ACT framework, focusing on willingness and values-driven behaviour.

Week 12-20: Consolidation and Relapse Prevention: Reinforced the integrated practices and their application in daily life. Developed personalized relapse prevention plans, identifying potential triggers and coping strategies. Conducted post-treatment assessments to evaluate progress and outcomes. (Twohig et al., 2006).

Procedure

The ethical clearance for conducting this research was obtained from the ethics committee of IIS (Deemed to be) University, Jaipur. The Data was collected from tertiary care mental health hospitals. Psychiatric centres and clinics in Jaipur Rajasthan. A total of 14 participants were found suitable for the research according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Participants who did not fulfil the criteria were excluded from the study and were referred to other professionals. Participants were recruited for the study on regular basis. They were informed about the nature and components of therapy. Informed consent in a written form was taken from all the patients. After obtaining informed consent, pre assessment was carried out. This included Case History Performa (developed for the study), Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsion Scale (Goodman et al., 1989), Valued Living Questionnaire (Wilson & Groom 2002), The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (Hayes et al., 2004), Self-Compassion Scale (Neff, 2003), and Equanimity Questionnaire (Shires & Cayoun, 2021). This was followed by psycho education and explanation of rationale of the therapy. The therapeutic programme consisted of 12-20 sessions spread over a period of 6-10

weeks including therapy, psycho education and post assessments. One month subsequent to the termination of therapy and post intervention assessment follow up session was taken with each patient to track their progress.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was done using IBM SPSS-25. Various descriptive statistics like Mean, SD, and Percentages and Inferential statistics like Dependent Sample t test were used.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

Socio-demographic Profile of the ACT Intervention Group (n = 14)

Variable	Category	n	%
Gender	Male	10	71.4
	Female	4	28.6
Marital Status	Unmarried	11	78.6
	Married	3	21.4
Family Type	Nuclear	11	78.6
	Joint	3	21.4
Residence	Urban	9	64.3
	Semi-Urban	2	14.3
	Rural	3	21.4
Education	Graduate	8	57.1
	Post-Graduate	6	42.9
Occupation	Student	8	57.1
	Employed	6	42.9
Age (Years)	Mean	25.14	
	SD	4.29	

Note. ACT- Acceptance and Commitment Therapy

The ACT Intervention group (n = 14) was characterized by a predominantly male (71.4%), unmarried (78.6%). The sample was predominantly from an urban area (64.3 %) population. Most participants belonged to nuclear families (78.6%) and had achieved at least a graduate level of education (57.1%). The group was composed mainly of students (57.1%), with a mean age of 25.14 years as mentioned in Table 1.

Table 2

Paired-Samples t-Test for ACT Group (N = 14)

Variable	M (Pre - Post)	SD	t	df	p	Cohen's d
OCD	3.36	2.70	4.66	13	<.001**	1.24
Self-Compassion	-0.53	0.21	-9.48	13	<.001**	2.52
Psychological Flexibility	5.36	4.83	4.15	13	.001**	1.11
Equanimity	-10.31	3.62	-10.65	13	<.001**	2.85
Values Importance	-13.52	10.17	-4.97	13	<.001**	1.33
Values Consistency	-13.77	7.97	-6.47	13	<.001**	1.73
Values Total	-19.28	17.25	-4.18	13	.001**	1.12

Note. M = mean difference (Pre-Post); p < .01. ;ACT: Acceptance and Commitment Therapy

Table 2 presents the outcomes of paired-samples t-tests assessing pre-to-post changes in the ACT intervention group (N = 14). Significant improvements were observed across all measured domains. OCD severity showed a substantial reduction (M = 3.36, SD = 2.70), t(13) = 4.66, p < .001, indicating marked symptom relief post-treatment. Twohig et al. (2010) and 2018 in their

demonstrated that ACT leads to significant reductions in OCD symptoms. with large effect sizes, comparable to or exceeding traditional treatments. Besides focusing on the relational experiences with thoughts, the patients learnt acceptance of thoughts as mere mental events and subsequently, it may have led to reduction in compulsions.

Self-compassion significantly increased ($M = 0.53$, $SD = 0.21$), $t(13) = 9.48$, $p < .001$ findings are supported by a study which showed that brief ACT intervention significantly increased self-compassion. Furthermore, the researchers proved that psychological flexibility was the mediator increasing the self-compassion scores and argue that for OCD patients. Wetterneck et al. (2013) found self-compassion as a act of courage that allows patients to face intrusive thoughts without self-judgment. Patients eventually learnt to be kinder to themselves and alleviate chronic shame and guilt arising out of their mental health condition. Psychological flexibility also improved ($M = 5.36$, $SD = 4.83$), $t(13) = 4.15$, $p = .001$. Participants showed a significant change in psychological flexibility. However, the mean difference ($M = 5.36$) is recorded as a positive value due to the scale's scoring (where lower scores indicate higher flexibility). A meta-analysis found a strong correlation between improvements in psychological flexibility and reductions in OCD symptoms (Bluett et al., 2014). Another study found that the therapeutic gains in ACT for OCD are specifically facilitated by increases in psychological flexibility (Twohig et al., 2015). ACT facilitated patients to develop flexibility in approaching their mental experiences.

Equanimity increased notably ($M = 10.31$, $SD = 3.62$), $t(13) = 10.65$, $p < .001$. Research by Juneau et al. (2020) suggests that as individuals develop the ability to accept thoughts without reacting, their level of equanimity increases, which serves as a protective factor against anxiety. Consistent with the previous findings, it was found that mindfulness enhances equanimity, allowing patients to stay undisturbed by intrusive thoughts (Desbordes et al., 2015). Values based living including importance ($M = 13.52$, $SD = 10.17$), $t(13) = 4.97$, $p < .001$; consistency ($M = 13.77$, $SD = 7.97$), $t(13) = 6.47$, $p < .001$; and total values score ($M = 19.28$, $SD = 17.25$), $t(13) = 4.18$, $p = .001$ also improved significantly. Consistent with these findings, Gupta et al. (2021) stated that ACT, instead of just focusing on symptom reduction, also emphasizes on the patient's functioning over symptom alleviation. This deviation from the traditional approach reduces the chances of relapse and enhances the generalization of valued skills. Capel and Twohig (2025) have also demonstrated in their study that values-based exposures lead to significant improvements in quality of life and active engagement in life, even when symptoms are still present.

Collectively, these findings demonstrate that the ACT intervention led to statistically robust changes in OCD severity and its associated psychological constructs, supporting Hypothesis 1. Strengths of the Study include focus on symptom reduction, the study includes process-based measures indicating how the treatment works, not simply the efficacy. The study also indicated that the ACT intervention had a large and clinically significant impact, suggesting it as a powerful tool. While the results are statistically significant, the small size of the ACT group limits the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the current data reflects Post-test results. It is unknown if these gains in Valued Living and OCD reduction are maintained 6 or 12 months later. However, the therapeutic process in this study shifts focus from stopping the thoughts to changing the relationship with thoughts. The significant increase in Values suggests that using values as the life compass can help OCD patients re-engage with life milestones that they previously couldn't engage with due to the obsessive and compulsive symptoms.

Conclusion

This intervention study provides credible evidence for the efficacy of

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) in managing obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) with mild to moderate severity. The results have shown that Acceptance Commitment Therapy intervention produces significant improvement in the patients, including both reduced symptom severity and enhancement of psychological processes that perpetuate the disorder. It can be understood that, by enhancing psychological flexibility and self-compassion, the therapy enabled a shift from a rigid and inflexible reactive approach with experiential avoidance to increased equanimity and emotional stability, further reducing shame and guilt proneness in the patients. The significant improvement in valued living consistency suggests that participants regained autonomy from the trap of OCD-related thoughts and behaviour, aligning daily actions and goals with their core values even with the presence of constant distressing intrusive thoughts. These findings support the stance that recovery in OCD is achieved by changing the patient's relationship with intrusive thoughts rather than completely eradicating them. And that symptom reduction occurs in the background as when the patient starts living a more even-minded, self-compassionate, and value-driven life. Overall, the study advocates for the integration of ACT into standard clinical utilisation, either as a standalone or adjunct therapy, offering a holistic approach to mental health that prioritizes recovery and value-based living over mere symptom reduction.

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